

Civil Society Organizations and Conflict Management in Nigeria: A Study of Academic Staff Union of Universities, 2013 – 2023

HAILSHAM, F. S. L., Ph.D & E.O. DAVIES, Ph.D

**¹Department of Adult Education and Community Development,
Faculty of Education, Rivers State University,
Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Corresponding Author's Email: lolohailsham@gmail.com**

**²Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated civil society organizations and conflict management in Nigeria with a focus on Academic Staff Union of Universities. The paper further examined the impact of university autonomy on conflict management, assess the effectiveness of university funding and explore the impact of politics and national issues debate on Nigerian universities and conflict management. The paper adopts field survey research which involves the use of both primary and secondary data. The theory of structural-functionalism is adopted while a sample of 50 lecturers were drawn from various federal universities to determine the strength of the investigation. Findings reveal that persistent conflict, leading to series of strike action by ASUU is the failure of the Federal Government of Nigeria to honour and implement previous agreements and memorandum of understanding. Poor budgeting, infrastructural decay and negotiations are taken for granted by Government. Based on this, the paper recommends among others that university autonomy's policy should be implemented to enhance the Nigerian university system. Infrastructural facilities should also be put in place to enhance learning while government honour agreements and negotiations entered with ASUU for an enhanced industrial harmony.

Keywords: Civil Society Organization, Conflict, Conflict Management, Academic Staff Union of Universities

I. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria and other parts of the world have been characterized by recurrent violent and non-violent conflict over issues involving the right of choice, freedom from ignorance and want, empowerment and capability, respect for the rule of law and equality before the law, promotion and defence of human rights, accountability, decentralization of power and authority, among others (Egobueze, 2021). The scholar opines that conflict also emanated in domestic marital matters, scarce resources, land, gender discrimination, clashes of interest, sexual assault, child abuse, family discrimination, economic burden, political clash, social disagreements, industrial disharmony, etc. he notes that it has also assumed ethnic, religious, political, resources, and family dimension with its attendant negative effects cannot be overemphasized etc. he claims that it is a natural and an integral part of human existence in every society and a disagreement between two people or groups; the process of living and interacting with one another

makes dispute inevitable. They are products of social structure and character of society of which local government council is an integral part (Ojum and Egobueze, 2022).

Alapiki (2010) who supports the claims above, reveals that disputes are not uncommon and are a part of growth and development. The scholar stresses that dispute can arise from diverse parties, amongst individuals, families, institutions, corporate bodies, different levels of government, communities etc. These disputes have diverse causes either from a claim of ownership over a property, or a violation of human right by an individual, state or political party. Supporting the above, Ushie, Igbaji & Agba (2015) argue that conflict is gaining prominence and has become almost synonymous with the existence of human organizations the world over. This reality is somewhat paradoxical when one considers the enormous amount of energy and resources expended by organizations world-wide to prevent and or resolve conflicts.

Conflict is not an exemption in Nigerian tertiary institutions. It has always occurred as a result of clashes of interest between the federal/state governments and Academic Staff Unions of Universities (ASUU). Egwu (2020) opines that the tertiary institutions in Nigeria are categorized into universities, polytechnics and colleges of education, with distinct structures, functional mandates and modus operandi but, however notes that the most frequent, the most far reaching and the most impactful conflicts is that involving Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and Government as university proprietors. According to Aina, Awolusi and Odunlami (2015), membership of ASUU covers both the federal and state universities, even though proprietary interests are separate. This makes conflicts involving ASUU and government far reaching, as strike and other industrial actions declared by the Union affect all public universities. ASUU negotiates key issues affecting federal universities with the federal government and agreements reached are expected to spill over to state universities. It follows that most of the conflicts involve ASUU and the federal government. Labour unionism is not allowed in private universities and their academic staff are not members of ASUU.

From the foregoing, conflict is a universal phenomenon. It involves a wide array of activities arising from individual, group, and organisations competing for interest which mostly relates to economic or welfare of members particularly in the case of ASUU. So far, conflicts in Nigerian universities have produced both positive and negative results. Positively, it helps to enhance academic progress and improve performances while it has created some senses of distrust against the government. However, the actual incidents of conflict which do not only exist in the mind but in physical display and manifestations, whereby there are expression of contradictory opinion on issues of policies, serious disagreement between two or more agents leading to strikes, and instances of strained relationships altogether constitute the strong notion of conflict.

Statement of Problem

Conflicts in Nigerian universities exist in many dimensions. Most times, it occurs between and amongst students, student unions, academic union, non-academic members/union and university management. These group of persons are organized into civil society organizations or labour unions for the purpose of protecting the interest and wellbeing of their members. However, conflicts in Nigeria universities can be said to be interpersonal or inter-group when they take the form of open actions such as hostile reactions or strike actions against other persons or group. These conflicts have produced both negative and positive effects. In its negative effect, conflict fosters distrust, resistance to change, antagonism, and disruption of academic programmes. Positively, it enhances effective performance through critical evaluation, innovation and change.

Excessive external control over finances, administration, appointment and recruitment is a bane to university development in Nigeria. The government through political gimmicks appoints their protégés to administer the affairs of universities is an aberration. The administration of finances which is determined by political agents do not portray the quality and products of the universities in good light. The entire management is seemed as rubber-stamp executives and do not have a say neither make meaningful contribution or inputs in the process leading to quality teaching environment. This has adverse effect on the the research skill and innovative abilities of both students and lecturers. The welfare of both academic

and non-academic staff of many universities have also been compromised where lecturers have become beggars leaving from hand to mouth. Several efforts aimed to address this menace prove abortive. This has made academic union to embarked on several strike actions while others have left the coastline of this country to search for a greener pasture abroad.

In this light of the above, this paper investigates CSOs and conflict management in Nigerian Universities with focus on Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), 2013 - 2023. The objectives are to:

- a. Examine the impact of university autonomy on conflict management in Nigerian universities;
- b. Assess the effectiveness of university funding on conflict management in Nigerian universities; and
- c. Explore the impact of politics and national issues on conflict management in Nigerian universities.

Theoretical Framework

Structural-Functionalism

The paper locates the structural-functionalism approach by Émile Durkheim in the 19th century. The approach is not only useful but appropriate in explaining conflict management in any society. Okonkwo (2008) notes that the theory which was the work of Émile Durkheim gained popularity in the fields of social sciences. The scholar further states that the theory was used by Herbert Spencer and Robert Merton to analyse the workings of the society, social behaviour and social phenomena in 1903. It was also adopted in the study of "Social Psychology of Organizations" by Daniel Katz and Robert Khan in 1966.

The theory as a concept stemmed from the conception that the societal administrative phenomena can best be analysed and understood by viewing them as parts of a systematic whole (Idakwoji, 2002). It is a framework for building theory that sees society as a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability. Its emphasis changed in the 1960s, however, with new challenges to the functionalist notion that a society's survival depended on institutional practices. The development and proper functioning of any society is linked to the interconnectivity and interdependency of the sub-systems. He emphasizes that there is need for the organization to interact with its environment since effectiveness and efficiency are expected outcomes of any organization. The central concern of structural-functionalism is a continuation of the task of explaining the apparent stability and internal cohesion or conflict of societies that are necessary to ensure their continued existence over time. Many functionalists argue that social institutions are functionally integrated to form a stable system and that a change in one institution will precipitate a change in other institutions. Societies are seen as coherent, bounded and fundamentally relational constructs that function like organisms, with their various parts (social institutions) working together to maintain and reproduce them. The various parts of society are assumed to work in an unconscious, quasi-automatic fashion towards the maintenance of the overall social equilibrium. All social and cultural phenomena are therefore seen as being functional in the sense of working together to achieve this state and are effectively deemed to have a life of their own. These components are then primarily analysed in terms of the function they play (Makoji, 2005). According to the scholar, structural-functionalism if followed would lead to precision, orderliness, efficiency and effectiveness in any organization or society. The ideal construct postulated by Ivuoma (2009) promotes the existence of a social society of control based on values, morals guided by rules which regulates the whole systemic structure and serves as apparatus for the achievement of conflict-free society.

The model therefore brings to light the interdependence of the various components, processes and functionality expected of an organization, with higher management facilitating system-base leadership, performance appraisal, staffing, compensation and reward, to ensure peaceful atmosphere or conduct. It views the universities as a complex amalgamation of many sub-processes aimed at increasing the capability of ASUU and other groups to contribute to conflict management process. The model adequately furnishes this paper with the theoretical assumptions that universities are inseparable aspects of government institutions and that for the process to be completed, conflict management is indispensable. Both ASUU and the government must function interdependently in conflict management to engender the

general improvement of both students and university workers. Nigeria is a system where the various structures such as the academic institutions, power sector, agricultural sector, etc must incorporate all the actors (unions) to function interrelatedly in their areas of proficient divisions with government or its agents to drive the development envisaged for tertiary institutions. Any attempt by the government to act in an opposite direction would amount to conflict. In which case, conflict management would fail.

Conceptual Clarifications

Concept of Civil Society Organizations

The term “civil society organizations” has been viewed differently by scholars and authors in the perception of their fields. As such, it does not have a universally acceptable definition. According to the United Nations, a Civil Society Organization (CSO) or non-governmental organization (NGO) is any non-profit, voluntary citizens’ group which is organized on a local, national or international level. The CSOs frame according to Habib and Rafique (2019), accumulate and prioritize preferences of citizens and help their representatives to take a collective action for overcoming their problems. The CSOs also help in developing the realization among politicians, government and bureaucracy of responsiveness and accountability and also highlight the repercussion in case of poor performance. Cooper (2016) defines civil society organisations (CSOs) as groups and networks vary by size, structure and platform ranging from international non-governmental organisations and mass social movements to small, local organisations. It is also important to note that civil society organizations develop as the state develops and are formed to respond to various needs and issues prevailing in the society. CSOs also can be based on various ideologies, occupation, profession or common beliefs. For instance, ASUU, SSANU, NASU, ASUP, and other unions that exist in tertiary institutions are institution-based CSOs. Some can be faith-based, economic-based among many others. Civil Societies have great importance to every state. As stated in the Civil Charter (2016), Civil society organizations engage in advocating the public’s rights and wishes of the people, including but not limited to health, environment and economic rights. They fulfil important duties of checks and balances in democracies, they are able to influence the government and hold it accountable. As stated earlier, Civil Societies now range of organic and organized groups which includes, NGOs (Non-Governmental Organizations), social movements, trade unions, grassroots organizations, faith groups, online networks and communities. Typologies of civil society further articulated include; NGOs, CSOs and non-profit organisations that have an organised structure or activity, and are typically registered entities and groups; Online groups and activities including social media communities that can be “organised” but do not necessarily have physical, legal or financial structures; Social movements of collective action and/or identity, which can be online or physical; Religious leaders, faith communities, and faith-based organisations; Labour unions and labour organisations representing workers; Social entrepreneurs employing innovative and/or market-oriented approaches for social and environmental outcomes; Grassroots associations and activities at local level; Cooperatives owned and democratically controlled by their members; Youth clubs; Independent radio, television, print and electronic media; Neighbourhood or community-based coalitions; Academic and research institutions; Organisations of indigenous peoples (Cooper, 2016).

Concept of Conflict

Conflict has become not only visible in recent times but volatile. This is not unconnected with the lucrateness of our educational institutions in Nigeria. Mayowa (2019) asserts that conflict is an unavoidable aspect of human interaction and an unavoidable concomitant of choices and decisions. The problem then is not to court the frustrations of seeking to remove inevitability but of trying to keep conflicts in bound (Zartman, 1991). In short, conflict is not an anathema; it is the whole essence of governance. It thus follows that any responsive government has the responsibility of responding to conflicts arising from the operations and activities of the political agents and the political subjects within the political system. In fact, how a government succeeds in conflict times determines the longevity of the administration or regime.

In the view of Mullins (1996) conflict is a product of opposing behaviours based on incompatibility of goals, "behaviour intended to obstruct the achievement of some other person's goals". Gardiner and Simmions (1992) defined the concept as any divergence of interest, objectives, or priorities between individual's groups or organizations or non-conformity to requirements of a task activity or process. Ihejiamaizu (1996) opines conflict with "an overt behaviour that results when an individual or group of individuals thinks a perceived need or needs of the individual or groups of individuals has been frustrated or is about to be frustrated. DeCenzo (1997) on the other hand submitted that whenever two people come together, there are bound to be disagreements at times. Sometimes, these differences can grow to enormous proportion where they become detrimental to the parties involved and the organizations. When that occurs, conflict is present. He added that conflicts can take the following forms: horizontal conflict, vertical conflict and role confusion/conflict. Conflicts, when poorly managed affect the accomplishment of organizational goals due to their attendant stress, hostilities, and other undesirable outcomes (Agba, Ushie & Agba, 2009). Rahim (1992) contends that conflict as an interactive process is manifested in incompatibility, disagreement or difference within or between social entities (that is, individual groups, organizations etc).

The foregoing revealed that conflict is the behaviour of an individual, a group, or an organization which impedes or restricts (at least temporarily) another party from attaining its deserved goals. Conflict is not necessarily a bad thing especially when well managed; constructive conflict can be a catalyst for improvement in an organization. It implies that conflicts have both positive and negative outcomes on an organization depending on how it is handled by management. It may be beneficial if it produces new information that enhances decision-making and overall performance of a system. It is associated with negative features if it gives rise to inefficiency, ineffectiveness, or dysfunctional consequences.

Concept of Conflict Management

Some conflict scholars have argued that complete resolution of conflict is impossible, but in a conflict situation, something needs to be done. The way out is to manage the conflict. According to Ogbujah and Egobueze (2021) conflict is endemic and inevitable, conflict management is equally inevitable especially the destructive type. Conflict management is therefore another permanent feature of any society. As a concept, it means a process of reducing the negative and destructive capacity of conflict through several measures and by working with and through the parties involved in that conflict. This is why it is often called conflict regulation or prevention (Best, 2012). Conflict management main concern covers the entire area of handling conflicts positively at different stages like conflict limitation, containment and litigation. In this sense, conflict management equally entails the ability of the person or group involved in bringing positive goal between the parties in the conflict to identify and handle conflict sensibly to ensure that all the parties involved in the conflict are fairly treated to reduce the pressure on them. Conflict management is not just an arrangement, but a long-time institutional arrangement, provisions and regulative procedures for dealing with conflict each time it occurs. It is as Kabe and Wilson (2018) in Ogbujah and Egobueze (2021) put it as a long-term process to enable the manager identify "wrong" and "right" ill of the conflict and establish the same before the parties involved. Deductively, conflict management is an activity, process, action plan to ameliorate, control/reduce negative conflict or destructive conflict and if possible, eliminate the capacity of such conflict to cause harm to the groups through several measures including the active participation of the parties in the conflict. According to Chima and Alokpa (2015), conflict management theorists "see conflicts as an ineradicable consequence of differences of values and interests within and between communities." These theorists regard resolving such conflicts as unrealistic: the best that can be done is to manage and reduce them, and occasionally to reach a historic compromise in which violence may be laid aside and normal politics resumed. Conflict management, according to Rahim (2002), is the attempt to keep a conflict from getting worse. Therefore, it involves the use of skills to control the intensity of a conflict and its effect through facilitation, negotiation and other kinds of intervention and institutional measures, as well as other means such as diplomacy.

From the definition, conflict management can be viewed from two equal perspectives-conflicts within the university (intra-university conflict) and conflict between the university and government (inter-area conflicts).

The focus of this paper is on conflicts between the universities and government (inter-area conflicts). The university is an institution recognized by law to train, teach or educate students and carry out other research activities that could breed socio-economic development and progress to the generality of people while utilising the efforts and engagement with public agencies and other relevant bodies within its domain to achieve relative peace. Conflictual issues arising between the universities and government are generally economical and political, mostly between and among political office holders and ASUU and other unions. Economic issues such as differences in welfare, unequal salaries, privileges, sharing formula, tax and revenue collection, control over treasury, local expenditure, unequal touring advances, unpaid allowances, university funding, university autonomy, IPPIS, research allocation, poor and inadequate manpower, excessive workloads, etc. The government and ASUU and other unions must adopt the process of identifying, explaining, settling, determining and resolving conflicts or issues between parties. It should be noted that the resolution of a conflict in its proper application means that the issues at stake has been settled to the satisfaction of all parties.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts field survey research which involves the use of both primary and secondary data. A sample of fifty (50) persons were selected randomly from a range of ASUU members who understand the intrigues, roles and challenges faced by international organizations, to constitute the sample population for the study. Data were obtained through the administration of structured questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire was structured into two sections. Section A entails the demographic attributes (sex, age, marital status, qualification, working experience, position) while the Section B centred on the main research and rated in 4-Likert scale with options of strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). Data obtained were presented using tables and simple percentage statistical method was used to determine degree of acceptance.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Table 1: Methodological Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency	Percentage
Number of questionnaires administered	50	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	10	20%
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	40	80%

Source: Field Work, 2024

The table above reveal that out of the 50 questionnaires administered to respondents, 10 making 20% of the questionnaires were not returned while 40 were successfully completed and valid for proper analysis. The response rate is 80% which is good for the study.

Table 2: Social and Demographic Background of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency (F)	Percentages (%)
Age bracket	18 - 40	20	50
	41 – 60	20	50
	Total	40	100
Gender distribution	Male	30	75
	Female	10	25
	Total	40	100
Rank in Education	Professorial cadre	5	13
	Senior Lecturer I & II	20	50
	Graduate Assistant	15	37
	Total	40	100

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 2 above shows that 20 respondents representing 50% are within the age bracket of 18-40 years while 20 (50%) are within the age bracket of 41-60 years. This indicates that stakeholders are abreast with

the issues under investigation. Also, the table above shows that 30 questionnaires representing 75% were administered to male while 10 questionnaires with 25% were female. This reveals that the respondents who attended to the questionnaires are mainly males. Notwithstanding, responses from both genders are analysed for a valid judgement. Finally, the table above depicts that 5 (13%) are in the professorial cadre; 20 (50%) respondents belong to Senior lecturer, lecturer I and II while 15 respondents representing 37% are graduate assistant. This shows that the respondents are dominated by different levels of graduates with various certificate holders. This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge about the subject matter or topic.

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of university autonomy on conflict management in Nigerian Universities?*

Table 3. Computation of response rate for the impact of university autonomy on conflict management in Nigerian Universities.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Total
Appointment of universities' principal officers in autonomy enhances Nigerian universities.	15 (37%)	15 (37%)	5 (13%)	5 (13%)	40 (100%)
University autonomy does not guarantee the political freedom of Nigerian Universities.	30 (75%)	5 (13%)	5 (13%)	0 (0%)	40 (100%)
Excessive political influence hinders university autonomy in conflict management in Nigerian Universities.	20 (50%)	10 (25%)	7 (18%)	3 (7%)	40 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

Table 3 ascertain the impact of university autonomy on conflict management in Nigerian Universities. It shows that 15 respondents representing 37% strongly agreed and agreed respectively while 5 representing 13% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. This indicates that appointment of universities' principal officers in autonomy enhances Nigerian universities. Also, 20 questionnaires representing 50% strongly agreed with 10 respondents representing 25% agreed while 5 questionnaires with 13% disagreed with 0 respondent strongly disagreed respectively. This reveals that university autonomy does not guarantee the political freedom of Nigerian Universities. The table above depicts that 20 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed with 10 (25%) agreed while 7 (18%) respondents disagreed with 3 respondents representing 7% strongly disagreed. This shows that excessive political influence hinders university autonomy in conflict management in Nigerian Universities.

Research Question 2: *How has university funding enhances conflict management in Nigerian Universities?*

Table 4: Computational analysis of response rate of the effectiveness of university funding on conflict management in Nigerian Universities.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Poor budgeting has made Nigerian Universities less effective in conflict management.	5 (13%)	30 (75%)	0 (0%)	5 (13%)	40 (100%)
University funding has not enhanced infrastructural facilities in Nigerian Universities.	10 (25%)	20 (50%)	3 (7%)	7 (18%)	40 (100%)
Poor implementation of ASUU-FG negotiation is a result of poor funding.	15 (37.5%)	15 (37.5%)	0 (0%)	10 (25%)	40 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

In their view on whether poor budgeting has made Nigerian Universities less effective in conflict management, 5 respondents represent 13% strongly agreed with 30 respondents representing 75% agreed while 0 (0%) “strongly disagreed” while 5 (13%) “disagreed”. This infers that poor budgeting has made Nigerian Universities less effective in conflict management. Also, 10 (25%) respondents strongly agreed, 20 (50%) respondents agreed while 3 (7%) respondents disagreed with 7 (18%) strongly disagreed respectively. Their responses reveal that University funding has not enhanced infrastructural facilities in Nigerian Universities. Finally, 15 respondents representing 37.5% strongly agreed, and agreed respectively while 0 respondents with 10 respondents representing 25% strongly disagreed. This implies that Poor implementation of ASUU-FG negotiation is a result of poor funding.

Research Question 3: *What is the impact of politics and national issues on Nigerian Universities and conflict management?*

Table 5. Computation of response rate on the impact of politics and national issues on Nigerian Universities and conflict management.

Questionnaires	Strongly Agreed f (%)	Agreed f (%)	Strongly Disagreed f (%)	Disagreed f (%)	Total
Government unfavourable policy affects university funding and conflict management in Nigerian Universities.	20 (50%)	15 (37.5%)	3 (7.5%)	2 (5%)	40 (100%)
There is poor commitment in payment of outstanding salaries and earned allowances in university education.	10 (25%)	20 (50%)	5 (13%)	5 (13%)	40 (100%)
Political instability and poor pension management affect university education in conflict management.	20 (50%)	11 (33%)	5 (13%)	4 (10%)	40 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2024.

In their view on whether government unfavourable policy affects university funding and conflict management in Nigerian Universities, 20 respondents which represent 50% strongly agreed with 15 respondents representing 37.5% agreed while 3(7.5%) disagreed with 2(5%) strongly disagreed. Also, 10 (25%) respondents strongly agreed, 20(50%) respondents agreed while 5(13%) respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that there is poor commitment in payment of outstanding salaries and earned allowances in university education. Finally, the table finds that political instability and poor pension management affect university education in conflict management with 20 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed, 11 respondents representing 33% agreed while 5 respondents representing 13% disagreed and 4 respondents representing 10% strongly disagreed.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Impact of University Autonomy on Conflict Management: Primary data shows the impact of university autonomy on conflict management in Nigerian Universities and reveals that 15 respondents representing 37% strongly agreed and agreed respectively while 5 representing 13% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. This indicates that appointment of universities’ principal officers in autonomy enhances Nigerian universities. Also, 20 questionnaires representing 50% strongly agreed with 10 respondents representing 25% agreed while 5 questionnaires with 13% disagreed with 0 respondent strongly disagreed respectively. This reveals that university autonomy does not guarantee the political freedom of Nigerian Universities. The table above depicts that 20 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed with 10 (25%) agreed while 7 (18%) respondents disagreed with 3 respondents representing 7%

strongly disagreed. This shows that excessive political influence hinders university autonomy in conflict management in Nigerian Universities. This is in line with a participant when he states that:

University autonomy is a scam. The government has introduced politics to take away university freedom from the system. It has been able to use this term or concept to hoodwink most of us so as to call-off strike and maintain industrial harmony. The appointment of governing councils and other principal officers of the universities are still being conducted by the government as against the wish of ASUU. This is bad for our university education (I. Iwedi, personal communication, August 15, 2024).

In line with the above, secondary data has also revealed that the concept of university autonomy, though as old as university education system in Nigeria, has remained a thorny and unresolved issue between ASUU and the Federal Government. The 1992 ASUU-FGN agreement and subsequent agreements and MOUs provided for university autonomy and academic freedom and in 2003, the University Miscellaneous Act was passed by the National Assembly and signed into law by the former President Olusegun Obasanjo. This Act was expected to bring to an end all controversial issues concerning university autonomy, including appointment of Vice Chancellors and other principal officers, funding of universities, the constitution of University Governing Councils and freedom to take decisions concerning academic structures and programmes. In spite of the passage of the University Miscellaneous Act of 2003, the appointment of Vice Chancellors and other key officers of the universities, both at federal and state levels, have continued to be politically influenced by the Chief Executives and has remained a major source of conflict (Aina et al (2015). Sanda (1992) views academic freedom as freedom to organize the university, design and structure the programmes, associate with others, hold and exchange ideas without any fear of victimization or harassment and challenge established orthodoxies without any fear of contradiction, all in the pursuit of truth. However, such incidence as outright ban on university staff and student associations, premature retirement, or rationalization of programmes as a result of government overregulation all result in decreasing autonomy (Alabi, 2002 cited in Aina et al (2015).

The effectiveness of University Funding on Conflict Management: Data analysis finds that poor budgeting has made Nigerian Universities less effective in conflict management, 5 respondents represent 13% strongly agreed with 30 respondents representing 75% agreed while 0 (0%) “strongly disagreed” while 5 (13%) “disagreed”. This infers that poor budgeting has made Nigerian Universities less effective in conflict management. Also, 10 (25%) respondents strongly agreed, 20 (50%) respondents agreed while 3 (7%) respondents disagreed with 7 (18%) strongly disagreed respectively. Their responses reveal that University funding has not enhanced infrastructural facilities in Nigerian Universities. Finally, 15 respondents representing 37.5% strongly agreed, and agreed respectively while 0 respondents with 10 respondents representing 25% strongly disagreed. This implies that Poor implementation of ASUU-FG negotiation is a result of poor funding. This view was corroborated by an interviewee who responded that:

Nigerian universities cannot play their roles in conflict management when government has reduced to make the environment conducive to thrive. As we speak, government’s budget to the university is very poor. There is infrastructural decay. Take a look at our structures; lack of maintenance, poor implementation of agreement by the FG entered with ASUU. There is absolute lack of university funding in conflict management (T. Eli, personal communication, August 20, 2024).

In consonance with the responses from the interviewee, Oyeniran (2013) took a retrospective look at education funding in Nigeria and observed that the general economic downturn of the 1980s resulted in instability and financial inadequacy for the Nigerian educational system. Since the oil crisis in the eighties, the proportion of capital budget allocated to education has been consistently lower than the

proportion of recurrent expenditure and over the years, the government capital expenditure allocated to education as a percentage of total capital budget ranged from as low as 1.71% in 1999 and in all cases below 9% (Oyeniran, 2013). The UNESCO (2000) World Education Report presents the data for nineteen countries across sub-Saharan Africa for 1996. The average share of GDP was 4.7% and of government expenditure was 19.6%. In both cases, the measures of educational expenditures for Nigeria, which recorded 2.3% and 14.3% respectively fall below average.

The direct consequences of inadequate funding of the universities (and other educational institutions) are fast deterioration of infrastructural facilities, including lecture halls, laboratories and halls of resident. Vital laboratory equipment and up-to-date library books and journals as well as e-learning facilities are grossly in short supply. Oyeniran (2013) presents a common phenomenon where students sit on bare floor or hang by the window side because lecture rooms cannot accommodate them. The issue of funding has been a major source of crisis between the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Federal Government. ASUU went on strike in 1992, 1993, 1994, 1996, 1999, 2001, 2003 and 2009 to press home its demand for increased funding for the university system (Aina, Awolusi and Odunlami, 2015). The inability of the Federal Government to implement the 26% ASUU-FGN negotiation of 1992 and 2001 has remained a source of conflict between ASUU and the Federal Government to date (Oyeniran, 2013).

Impact of Politics and National Issues on Conflict Management: Data analysis reveals that government unfavourable policy affects university funding and conflict management in Nigerian Universities. 20 respondents which represent 50% strongly agreed with 15 respondents representing 37.5% agreed while 3(7.5%) disagreed with 2(5%) strongly disagreed. Also, 10 (25%) respondents strongly agreed, 20(50%) respondents agreed while 5(13%) respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that there is poor commitment in payment of outstanding salaries and earned allowances in university education. Finally, the table finds that political instability and poor pension management affect university education in conflict management with 20 respondents representing 50% strongly agreed, 11 respondents representing 33% agreed while 5 respondents representing 13% disagreed and 4 respondents representing 10% strongly disagreed. Responding to this, a participant reveals that:

The Nigerian government at every time scores “A1” in playing politics with the universities. Most time, when ASUU places a demand, the government would paint it as an agitation sponsored by opposition party. They make unfavourable policy and plays politics with payment of outstanding salaries and earned allowances. Where is the place of university funding and effective service delivery when pension management is poor with poor condition of service and illegal deductions. Politics overrides the process when government is insensitive to education (G. Barivure, personal communication, August 25, 2024).

Although, ASUU does not place the issue of enhanced conditions of service in the forefront of its demands on government to avoid negative public reactions, the question of brain drain and the need to upgrade university staff service conditions to international standard has continued to re-echo in ASUU-FGN negotiations (Ayodele and Adewumi, 2007). Ekundayo (2012) holds the view that the wide gap between the remuneration of university lecturers in Nigeria and their counterparts in other parts of the world accounts for the persistent crisis between the unions and government.

Government exerts a lot of influence on university administration. The appointment of key officers, such as Vice Chancellors, by the President and Governors for federal and state universities respectively have political undertone. The Federal Government, through the Federal Ministry of Education and National Universities Commission (NUC), controls the structure, curriculum, budget and calendar of the universities. The Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), a creation of the Federal Government, controls and manipulates admission to tertiary institutions in Nigeria. With such overwhelming influence over university administration with political coloration, conflict is bound to exist

between ASUU and government, particularly where the leadership of the union has opposing political leaning. Again, ASUU's functional objectives cover issues that border on socio-economic wellbeing of the generality of the masses. It is for this reason that unpopular government policies and programmes, which precipitate adverse reactions from national labour unions, equally receive strong resistance from ASUU. Examples include the issue of subsidy removal and hike in fuel prices by the immediate past regime, as well as the annulment of June 12, 1993 Presidential election.

After unsuccessful efforts, including warning strike, aimed at obtaining positive reactions from government, ASUU on 13th August, 2017 declared an indefinite strike to express its grievance against the Federal Government for non-implementation of the 2013 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the Union and the Federal Government, as well as the 2009 agreement (The Nation, 2017). Other demands as expressed in ASUU document include:

- a. Provision of funds for rehabilitation of public universities.
- b. Payment of outstanding salaries and earned allowances.
- c. Registration of Universities' Pension Management Company and pension matters.
- d. Reopening of Universities Staff Schools to be funded by Government as part of universities.

Conflict Management Strategies

Management scholars and researchers have identified various styles and strategies for management of conflict (Fisher, 2010). Ajike et al (2015) identified Blake and Mouton (1964) as the first management scholars to conceptualize the classification of conflict management styles into five, namely: avoiding, obliging, dominating, compromising and integrating. Other writers and researchers have similar classifications with varying shades and perspectives.

Thomas (1978) quoted in Hicks and Gullett (1981) avers that all responses to conflict situation involve degrees of assertiveness (trying to satisfy one's own concerns) and degrees of cooperativeness (trying to satisfy another's concerns). The combination of these two kinds of behaviour at varying degrees result in five common conflict management styles, similar to those identified by Blake and Mouton (1964). The first is avoiding, a conflict management strategy, which seeks to delay, ignore, or put off conflict indefinitely with the hope that the problem resolves itself without a confrontation. Although avoiding is often associated with position of low power or low esteem, it can sometimes be a useful conflict management strategy, for example, after dismissal of a popular but unproductive employee, the hiring of a more productive replacement for the position may placate the conflict situation created by the dismissal.

The second strategy identified by Thomas (1978) is accommodation. Accommodation, also referred to as smoothing, is a conflict management strategy which seeks to accommodate the concerns of opposing party first of all, rather than one's own concerns. It locates at the extreme axis of cooperativeness and depicts a position of apparent weakness, which may negatively affect one's ability to respond to aggressive opponent. However, accommodation can be usefully used if the circumstance requires buying time for a better position to respond, or reassess the situation from another angle. It can be used where the issue at stake is not as important to one party as it is to the other. An example is in the Nigerian banking industry, which requires formal dress code, but many banks allow casual dresses on Fridays to satisfy the yening of generality of staff. At the extreme axis of assertiveness is competition, also known as forcing, which operates as a zero-sum game, in which one side wins and the other loses. One party to the conflict, with assertive personalities, uses whatever power at its disposal to satisfy its concerns without regard to the concerns of the other party.

Forcing or competing strategy can be effectively used in few conflict situations, such as when less-forceful methods don't work, or there is need to stand up for one's own right, or when force is required for a quick resolution in the face of apparent threat to healthy corporate existence.

Another alternative approach is compromising, which seeks for mutually acceptable solution that is partially satisfactory to both parties but completely satisfactory to neither party. Compromising, which produces faster resolution of conflict, may be appropriate in a situation where temporary settlement of complex issues is required, or as a first step when parties involved have not yet developed reasonable

level of mutual trust. However, compromising may result in a lose-lose situation, where both parties are not satisfied with the outcome. It may not contribute to building trust in the long run and may require close monitoring and control to ensure that the parties respect the agreement. Finally, collaboration is a problem-solving strategy, which seeks a win-win solution that most satisfies the concerns of both parties to the conflict (Rose et al, 2006). This strategy sees conflict management as an opportunity to achieve a mutually beneficial result by identifying the concerns of the conflicting parties and finding solution that meets the expectations of the parties. Collaboration is feasible where a long-term relationship is important and there exists a high level of mutual trust.

The five conflict management strategies, as discussed above, have their merits and demerits. Rahim (2002) noted that there is agreement among management scholars that there is no one best approach to how to make decisions, lead or manage conflicts. Each of the strategies can be usefully applied to effectively address a conflict situation, depending on the circumstances, the environmental factors, the nature of the conflict and the parties to the conflict (Pruitt, 1983). The success or failure of any strategy depends on the situation. Where a wrong strategy is adopted, effective resolution of conflict becomes unachievable. This is the problem with the management of conflict between Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Nigerian Government.

CONCLUSION

The paper investigated civil society organizations and conflict management in Nigeria with a focus on the role of Academic Staff Union of Universities. The paper further examined the impact of university autonomy on conflict management, assess the effectiveness of university funding and explore the impact of politics and national issues debate on Nigerian universities and conflict management. Findings reveal that persistent conflict, leading to series of strike action by ASUU is the failure of the Federal Government of Nigeria to honour and implement previous agreements and memorandum of understanding. Poor budgeting, infrastructural decay and negotiations are taken for granted by Government. More often than not, Government negotiating team is headed by a nonexecutive who has no power to commit the Government. At one point in time, Government may adopt avoiding strategy, ignoring threats and warnings from ASUU with the hope that delay will bring solution. At some other time, Government may resort to forcing strategy, using the threat of “no work, no pay” in an effort to intimidate the workers. The flaws discussed above do not engender university harmony and conflict management in Nigerian Universities.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are made:

1. University autonomy's policy should be implemented to enhance the Nigerian university system. Collaboration strategy should be adopted in managing ASUU/Government conflicts.
2. The government should make an upward review of budget allocated to Nigerian universities. Infrastructural facilities should be put in place to enhance learning while government honour agreements and negotiations entered with ASUU for an enhanced industrial harmony.
3. Both government and ASUU should not play politics particularly when it appears to be a national issue. Government should make all outstanding payment and earned allowances and ensure that pension of university staff is adequately managed.

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Hailsham & Davies*Int. J. Inno. Psychology & Social Devept* 13(2): 63-76, 2025

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